

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 2**

Community database creation & management

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Milestone	30/01/2019 (M1)
Actual Achievement Date	30/04/2019 (M4)
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	10. Trust-IT
Work Package	WP 2 Communication, Dissemination and Impact
Task	T2.1 SSHOC cluster communication & dissemination strategy
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Abstract:

This milestone report described the SSHOC Stakeholder and the SSHOC Community databases created and managed.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
Trust-IT	Marieke Willems	m.willems@trust-it-services.com
Trust-IT	Leonardo Marino	l.marino@trust-it-services.com

1. Introduction

As described in the SSHOC GA, task 2.1 SSHOC cluster communication & dissemination strategy will produce a detailed communication and outreach plan, according to which a coordinated set of actions will be carried out, to ensure coverage of stakeholders and adequate visibility across Europe and beyond as well as a coherent, harmonized and communication following a cluster strategy. As part of this plan, communication objectives will be defined, and a well delineated stakeholder map and analysis will be conducted in collaboration with WP6 (T6.1).

In M2 the SSHOC Community Database and at M4, the SSHOC Stakeholder database were created and managed. The Stakeholder Database was shared with all participants in the common working space, whereas the SSHOC community database is managed in alignment with the GDPR requirements.

2. Description of the Milestone

During the SSHOC Kick-Off meeting, WP2 and WP6 identified opportunities to leverage on related activities for stakeholder engagement in WP6 and community building in WP2. After identification and alignment of the needs in both WPs, the WP2 SSHOC Community Database was merged with the WP6 SSHOC Stakeholder mapping database. With the aim to map the SSHOC stakeholders as identified in D2.1 and D6.1 and to identify the contact points to the different groups within the SSHOC project for targeted engagement.

FIGURE 1: SSHOC STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFIED

The **SSHOC Stakeholder Database** aimed to leverage on the effort from all partners in stakeholder and community engagement. All partners with stakeholder communities relevant to SSHOC project aims were asked to list these in the database, for both WP2 and community building and WP6 stakeholder engagement. For each stakeholder the following information is collected:

- Stakeholder to be targeted
- Extended name of organisation
- Description
- Country

- Stakeholder category (drop-down menu with: Researchers, Libraries & Archives, Research Funding Organisations, Civil Society and Citizen Scientists, Policy Making Organisations and Private Sector and Industry Players (see Image)
- Discipline (drop-down menu with detailed SSH subdomains)
- SSHOC Partners that links to this organisation
- Relevant SSHOC WPs
- Does the stakeholder provide training? Yes/No
- Communication channels in place
- Training geographical level (national/regional/international)
- Training Page URL
- Training geographical level (national/regional/international)
- Level of contact on SSHOC stakeholder (low/medium/high)

This database does not contain personal data, only information on organisational level and publicly available. The Database was set in place by 30 April 2019 and shared with the consortium in the Google Drive.

In August 2019, the database was moved to the SSHOC Shared Drive, into the SSHOC internal document repository, available to all Consortium partners¹.

In addition, SSHOC WP2 built a second database for the project, the **SSHOC community database** for direct communication with stakeholders and end-user communities on the activities of SSHOC. To comply with the GDPR, all entries in the Community Database that will be used for communication ends, need to have given specific consent.

Therefore, SSHOC needs to build this Database from scratch and will provide all project partners with standard messages to invite SSHOC target stakeholders in their networks to register for this database at the SSHOC website, having the possibility to choose subscription to SSHOC newsletters and updates or not. Contacts in this database will not be shared and will be saved and maintained complying with to the GDPR demands.

¹ Direct link to the SSHOC Stakeholder Database: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1kIRFolm-YJLcrdwjgSkzX2lwG3l4yOpwQIWDvPMAoTE/edit#gid=0> [accessed June 2020].; Note that the SSHOC Shared Drive internal project document repository is available only the Consortium partners; After the finalisation of the project it will be archived by project coordinator.

Sources of input to this database are:

- Newsletter subscription
- SSHOC Community and subcommunity registration: e.g. training community and Marketplace tester community.
- Webforms for events registration
- Webinar registrations
- Surveys

The SSHOC Community Database was set in place with the launch of the project website on 28 February 2019.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

SSHOC will use various communication channels leveraging on the project partner networks and will produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. The main channels that will be utilised in SSHOC are visualized in the figure below:

FIGURE 2: ELEMENTS DETERMINING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.

The SSHOC community database will provide WP2 and WP6 with an overview of stakeholder community and the identification of contact points to the different groups within the SSHOC project for targeted engagement.

2.2. Means of verification

On 30 April 2019 the SSHOC Stakeholder Database was shared with project partners in the SSHOC Shared Drive internal document repository, available to all Consortium partners². Internal mails to the consortium asking for input, as well as messages via the SSHOC basecamp environment.

FIGURE 3. BASECAMP ANNOUNCEMENT TO PROJECT PARTNERS

² Direct link to the SSHOC Stakeholder Database: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1kIRFolm-YJLcrdwjgSkzX2lwG3l4yOpwQIWDvPMAoTE/edit#gid=0> [accessed June 2020].; Note that the SSHOC Shared Drive internal project document repository is available only the Consortium partners; After the finalisation of the project it will be archived by project coordinator.

On 28 February 2019 the SSHOC Community Database was set in place, with the launch of the project website. One can register via webforms, events, subcommunities, newsletter or joining the SSHOC community at the URL: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/user/register>. Visible from the top bar of the project's homepage.

FIGURE 4. SSHOC HOMEPAGE TOP BAR OPTIONS

3. Conclusions and next steps

The SSHOC Stakeholder database is a living database, shared in the SSHOC Shared Google Drive, and updated as needed during the project lifetime.

The SSHOC Community database is constantly updated by new registrants and connections collected via the defined mechanisms.

In addition to these databases, the SSHOC social media channels form another pool of actively engaged community members.